

Jitter Control for Imaging Spacecraft

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Abstract— The current imaging spacecraft design trend is for higher imaging performance, allowing very low jitter. Vibration sources on spacecraft include reaction or momentum wheels, control moment gyros (CMG), solar drive motors, thruster firing, cryogenic coolers and slew maneuvers. Several techniques have been developed to reduce jitter. One technique is to increase damping of the spacecraft support structure to reduce vibration response by adding passive and/or active damping. The second technique is to introduce isolation between vibration source and the spacecraft. The third technique is to isolate the optical payloads from the spacecraft. The fourth technique is to reduce jitter in the optical beam by using fast steering mirrors. For spacecraft requiring the very low jitter, a combination of these techniques is used. This paper discusses briefly all these jitter control techniques.

Keywords—Jitter Control; Imaging Spacecraft

I. INTRODUCTION

To meet the image performance requirements, imaging spacecraft have very strict requirements for jitter. For some high performance spacecraft, the jitter requirements are in nano-radians. The current imaging spacecraft design trend is for higher imaging performance, allowing very low jitter. Vibration sources on spacecraft include reaction or momentum wheels (discrete frequencies related to wheel speeds and harmonics), control moment gyros (CMG) (discrete frequencies related to CMG speed and harmonics), solar drive motors, thermal shocks (especially solar arrays transitioning from eclipse to non-eclipse and vice versa), thruster firing (create jitter), cryogenic coolers (discrete frequencies), and slew maneuvers (effect entire spacecraft structure and associated frequencies).

The Figure 1 shows different techniques for reducing jitter for optical payloads. Several techniques have been developed to reduce jitter. One techniques is to increase damping of the spacecraft support structure to reduce vibration response by adding passive and/or active damping. The second technique is to introduce isolation between vibration source and the spacecraft. The third technique is to isolate the optical payloads from the spacecraft. The fourth technique is to reduce jitter in the optical beam by using fast steering mirrors. For spacecraft requiring very low jitter, a combination of these techniques is used. This paper discusses all these jitter control techniques

Figure 1: Vibration Control Techniques

II. VIBRATION CONTROL TECHNIQUES

A. Passive Damping Mechanism

All passive damping treatments share a common goal: absorb significant amounts of strain energy in the modes of interest and dissipate this energy through some energy-dissipation mechanism. The effectiveness of all passive damping methods varies with frequency and temperature, though some more than others. For each of the basic passive damping mechanisms, there are several choices for implementation, which can be divided into two major categories: discrete and distributed. Table 1 summarizes the primary passive damping concepts along with their typical uses.

Figure 2: Typical Viscoelastic Material Configuration

Viscoelastic materials are widely used for damping in both commercial and aerospace applications. Viscoelastic materials are elastomeric materials whose long-chain molecules cause them to convert mechanical energy into heat when they are deformed. Complex arithmetic provides a convenient means for keeping track of the phase angle by which an imposed cyclic stress leads the resulting cyclic strain.

Table 1: Passive Damping and Associate Design Methods

Type of Treatment						
	Strut/Link Dampers	Constrained Layers	Tuned-Mass Dampers	Joint/Interface Dampers	Embedded Dampers	Unconstrained or Free Layers
Target Modes	Global	Member Bending and Extension	Narrow Freq Range, any Mode Shape	Local or Global	Member Bending and Extension	Member Extension and Bending
Primary Design Method	Modal Strain Energy	Modal Strain Energy	Complex Eigenvalues	Joint Test or Modal Strain Energy	Modal Strain Energy	Hand Calc. Modal Strain Energy
Special Features	Removable, Light weight	Flexible, Wide Bandwidth	Low Cost, Low Volume	Low Weight, Low Volume	Embedded, Low Outgassing	Low Cost, Easy Design

Viscous Devices

A basic viscously damped isolator is depicted in Figure 3. Fluid of a specified viscosity is hermetically sealed within two sets of bellows and constrained to flow between them through an orifice when motion occurs. The fluid flow through the orifice provides the damping. A third set of bellows is included to accommodate thermal expansion and contraction of the fluid. Springs are included to provide the desired isolator stiffness. For safety, the device is encased in an outer skirt to protect against contamination from a ruptured bellows. This unit isolator can be simply modeled as a spring in parallel with a spring-damper. By changing the damping (fluid viscosity) of the isolator, the in-band peaking of the isolation characteristic can be changed, but at the cost of isolation bandwidth. Variations in temperature have a similar effect because of its affect on fluid viscosity.

Figure 3: Basic Viscous Fluid Damper

The D-Strut is one of the most common applications of viscous systems. In a classical spring-mass system, i.e., one that can be modeled with a single spring in parallel with a dashpot, the amplitude of damping is varied with a change in the damping coefficient; however, a more general representation of a viscous damper or D-Strut includes a second spring in series with the dashpot. The series spring (K_B) is usually very stiff compared to the parallel spring (K_A) and is often ignored; however, in many cases it can be used to improve performance. Its existence converts the system from a two-parameter to a three-parameter system, enhancing the opportunity for tuning the system or making the system adaptable. In the three-parameter system, changing the damping coefficient changes the frequency at which damping occurs, rather than the amplitude of the damping. At low frequency, the impedance is given by a static stiffness K_A , and at high frequency the stiffness increases to $K_A + K_B$. In the transition frequency range, the impedance is complex and the phase is leading. The magnitude of damping is related to the phase angle θ or the loss factor η . Note that the peak magnitude of η is related to the ratio of stiffness parameters K_B/K_A and is independent of the damping coefficient C_A . The frequency at which the peak phase angle (ϕ_0) or loss factor (η_0) occurs is ω_0 , and is inversely proportional to C_A .^{1,2,3}

Figure 4: Passive D-Strut

Magnetic Devices

Magnetic isolation is achieved by using two opposing electro-magnets acting on an armature plate. The key to the technology is in the non-contacting interference. This avoids the coupling paths, which are inherent in mechanical isolators, enabling magnetic suspensions to readily achieve a very large dynamic isolation range (greater than 80 dB). A typical magnetic isolator consists of two opposing horseshoe electromagnets acting on an armature plate. The electromagnets are mounted to the base, the passive armature is attached to the payload, and they are separated by a large air gap. Advantages of magnetic isolation are:

- Non-contacting interface
- Faster isolation roll-off of degrees of freedom (typically 100 dB/decade)
- Ease of adjustment (mode changes, structural uncertainties)
- Automatic alignment and centering (unbalance compensation)

● Non-contaminating materials

Figure 5: magnetic Isolation Description

Passive Piezoelectrics

Piezoelectric ceramic materials have the unique ability to produce a strain when subjected to an electrical charge, and, conversely, they produce a charge when strained mechanically (piezoelectric theory explained in subsequent section). This property has made them popular as actuators and sensors in active vibration control systems. This dual transformation ability also makes them useful as passive structural dampers. In passive energy dissipation applications, the electrodes of the piezoelectric are shunted with a passive electric circuit. The electrical circuit is designed to dissipate the electrical energy that has been converted from mechanical energy by the piezoelectric.

Tuned Mass Dampers

The use of tuned mass dampers (TMD) is another widely used passive vibration damping treatment. These devices are viscously damped 2nd order systems appended to a vibrating structure. Proper selection of the parameters of these appendages, tunes the TMD to one of the natural frequencies of the underdamped flexible structure, resulting in the addition of damping to that resonance. TMD's can target any mode, including the first, and add a considerable amount of damping to it.

Figure 6: Tuned Mass Dampers

The mass of the TMD and its stiffness are chosen to make the natural frequency of the TMD match to the resonant frequency of the beam to be damped. The damping effectiveness of a TMD is dependent on its damping ratio and the frequency it is tuned at. The lack of large enough damping ratio in the TMD results in breaking the resonant mode, to which the device is tuned for, to two underdamped modes – a phenomenon known as “mode splitting”. A damping ratio between 20 to 45 is an effective damping treatment using a TMD. The capability of tuned mass dampers to damp out a particular mode of vibration is due to the 90 degree phase lead that the TMD adds to the open loop system at the natural

frequency of that mode, along with a gradual change in its phase angle around that frequency.^{8,9}

B. Active Vibration Control

Voice Coils

Voice coil actuators are versatile direct drive, hysteresis-free, cog free, non-commuted, limited motion servo motors with linear control characteristics. The basic setup is a permanent magnet field assembly in conjunction with a coil winding that produces a force proportional to the current which is applied to the coil (see Figure 9). The magnets are of the same polarity. When current is applied to the circumferentially wound coil, it interacts with the radial magnetic field of the permanent magnet assembly via the Lorentz Force Principle to create an axial force (mutually perpendicular to the vectors of the current flow and the magnetic field) between the coil and the magnetic assemblies. The polarity of the current-producing voltage applied to the two terminals of the coil dictates the direction of the force on the coil and therefore stroke movement. The air gap between the magnet and coil assemblies is usually 0.01 – 0.015 inches. Because there is no contact between the moving parts, voice coil controlled devices are more reliable than hydraulic or pneumatic devices.

Figure 7: Generalized Active/Passive Performance Comparison

Figure 8: Voice Coil Schematic

Active Piezoelectrics

Piezoelectric ceramics can be used as strain sensor. The phase lead, 90 degrees is introduced into the output of the strain sensor and is fed into piezoelectric ceramics as actuator. It will increase damping of the structure.

C. Vibration Isolation

Vibration isolation platforms are used to isolate the optical payload from spacecraft vibration. Control algorithms have been developed for two platforms at the Naval Postgraduate School.

Ultra Quiet Platform (UQP)

The Ultra Quiet Platform (UQP) is used for testing control algorithms for vibration isolation of an imaging payload. It is configured similar to a six degree of freedom “cubic” Stewart Platform where the struts are arranged as if they were on the edges of a cube, providing for three orthogonal pairs of actuators.

In such arrangements, control in six degrees of freedom is possible using linear actuators, and the coupling between actuators is minimized. The UQP is mounted on a spacecraft mockup, to which is mounted an Aura Bass shaker which serves as the disturbance source. The entire experiment sits on sixteen rubber feet attached to a 3800 lb. Newport RS4000 isolation table which uses four Newport I-2000 series laminar flow isolator pneumatic pedestals to help further isolate the experiment from floor vibration.

Each strut consists of a piezoceramic stack actuator (PZT) and a geophone sensor. The PZT converts control signal voltages to physical movement of the strut. The maximum displacement of the actuator is 50 μ m, which is sufficient for vibration applications, but not for platform pointing/steering. The Geospace GS-11D geophone sensors consists of wire coils supported by soft springs under the influence of a magnetic field, which provides a signal proportional to velocity. The source of disturbance for the disturbance rejection experiment is an Aura Bass shaker (Model AST-1B-4, 25 W, 4 ohm).⁴

Figure 9: Ultra Quiet Platform (UQP)

The experiment requires power amplification for the actuators and signal conditioning for the geophone sensors. These are provided via a PCB Piezotronics 790A06 6-channel power amplifier (2000 V, 100 mA), and a CSA Engineering Active Vibration Control System (AVCS) signal-conditioning unit, respectively. The control function is performed by the combination of a dSPACE DSP system and a host PC. Coding for the control algorithms is performed in the Matlab/Simulink environment using C-coded “S-functions” to perform the more specialized tasks.

Precision Pointing Hexapod (PPH)

The Precision Pointing Hexapod (PPH) experimental platform is used for testing control algorithms for both vibration isolation of an imaging payload and fine steering. The PPH is based on an arrangement of six self-supporting electromagnetic voice coil actuators with in-line accelerometers that could enable control of higher vibration. Lower frequency steering and vibration isolation is provided by the use of laser/photo-diode based 2-axis position detecting system and eddy current position sensors. The system is capable of delivering significant range of motion in all six degrees of rigid body motion. It can deliver over 5.7 mm of axial/position travel, 20 mm of lateral motion, 2.5 deg. of tilt motion and 10 deg. of twist.⁴

Figure 10 Precision Pointing Hexapod

D. Optical Beam Control

For fine jitter control, optical beam jitter is controlled by fast steering mirror. Inertial reference unit provides jitter free reference laser and a sensor measures the jitter in the spacecraft and fast steering mirror is used to correct it. The image beam passes through the same path and so the jitter due to spacecraft is corrected. At the NPS⁵, several control algorithms have been developed to improve jitter control performance. The testbed is as follows.

Figure 11: Jitter Control Testbed

Jitter Control Algorithm

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To develop improved techniques for optical beam jitter control, a Laser Jitter Control (LJC) Testbed was developed at the Naval Postgraduate School as shown in Fig 11 and Fig 12. The components are mounted on a Newport optical bench, which can be floated to isolate the components from external vibrations. The laser beam originates from a source and passes through a Disturbance Injection Fast Steering Mirror (DFSM). The DFSM corrupts the beam using random or periodic disturbances simulating disturbances that might originate with the transmitting station or tip and tilt errors which the beam may suffer as it passes through the atmosphere. A vibration isolation platform is used to mount the relay system and to isolate the relay system from the optical bench. A control Fast Steering Mirror (FSM), designated the CFSM, is used to correct the disturbed beam. The corrected beam is then reflected off the platform to the target Position Sensing Detector (PSD).

Figure 12: Schematic of the laser jitter control testbed

For laser jitter control, Least Mean Square (LMS), Filtered-X LMS (FXLMS), and Recursive Least Square (RLS) filters were extensively evaluated and improvements were developed in these techniques. The improvement focus was to increase the convergence rate which results in an increased jitter reduction rate. This was done by adding two filters, an Adaptive Bias Filter (ABF) and an Adaptive Phase Filter (APF). A Linear Quadratic Regulator (LQR) was also used in parallel with adaptive filters in some cases.

Experimental Results

Figure 13. Power spectral density for jitter control methods

Experiments were performed to verify the control methods including the FXLMS and FXRLS designs. The results of FXLMS and FXRLS methods are compared with LQG control techniques with/without classical notch filters for sinusoidal disturbance rejection. Fig 13 shows the power spectral density of the signal across the frequency spectrum from 0 to 100 Hz. The mean squared error plot shown in Fig 14 shows that the FXRLS method manages to further reduce the mean square error of the signal compared to the FXLMS and LQG designs.

A summary for the sinusoidal disturbance at 50Hz, LQG with a notch filter provides the best performance. However, to apply this technique, the disturbance frequency must be accurately known and an error or change in disturbance frequency will degrade the performance significantly. Overall FXRLS provides superior performance.

Figure 14: Mean squared error for jitter control methods

III. SPACE APPLICATIONS

NASA Hubble Space Telescope Vibration Suppression^{6,7,8}

The National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) Hubble Space Telescope (HST) requires telescope-pointing accuracy of 0.01 arc sec. The spacecraft's attitude control system reaction wheels generate low level, high frequency vibration disturbances from imperfections in the electromagnetics and drive electronics, unbalance of the rotor, and imperfections in the spin bearings. The Viscous Fluid Damped Isolator, shown in Figure 15, developed by Honeywell, Inc., is a passive system employing metal springs in parallel with viscous fluid dampers, providing independent, deterministic control of the stiffness and damping characteristics.

Damping fluid is contained by two metal bellows supporting the center isolation portion. When the center portion moves axially, fluid must flow from one bellows chamber to the other, incurring viscous losses as it flows. The damping value is determined by the viscosity of the fluid and the dimensions of the annular passage between the chambers, while the stiffness value is determined by the bellows design. Coil springs are added in parallel and a third preloaded bellows chamber is added outboard to accommodate thermal fluid

expansion. Mechanical stops limit maximum displacements and redundant leak-proof seals minimize the chance of fluid escape. From testing, stiffness and damping were found constant over a disturbance amplitude range from 0.2×10^{-6} to 0.04 in. input displacement, or better than 0.007 arc sec.

Figure 15: HST Viscous Fluid Damped Isolator

CSA Engineering, Inc. designed and built a passive vibration isolation system, the Axial Scientific Instrument Protective Enclosure (ASPIE), to protect the Near-Infrared Camera / Multi-Object Spectrometer (NICMOS) payload that launched on the February 1997 STS-82 mission as part of the second servicing mission for HST. Primary requirements on the isolation system are a very long stroke (10.0 inches) and operation in a temperature range of -40 to $+65$ deg C. In response to fluid leakage concerns for struts, CSA Engineering integrated fluid-free isolation struts using magnetic eddy current dampers, or M-Struts, within the ASPIE system. For STS transport of future Orbital Replacement Units (ORUs) on the HST, CSA Engineering has developed two methods for launch vibration load suppression: an open / closed cell foam design that provides the required damping and corner frequency attenuation, and a Viscoelastic Material (VEM) design.

Figure 16: Vibration Suppression Systems on STS-82, 2nd HST Servicing Mission

The flexible solar array panels currently on the HST (SA-2) will be replaced with greater power generating rigid panels (SA-3) as part of STS Servicing Mission 3B (SM-3B)

scheduled for 2001. Analysis of the rigid solar array design shows the HST's pointing control system stability margin will be violated by the new array's fundamental bending modes. CSA Engineering has designed and built a damper, integrated into the SA-3 mast, constructed of a titanium flexure and viscoelastic damping material, which is temperature dependent. Fixed-base modal testing has shown that peak critical damping with the flight units is expected to be 3.7% of critical at approximately 10 deg C. The required damping level of 2.25% of critical is expected for the temperature range of -2 deg to 25 deg C for the in-plane bending mode, and 0 deg to 27 deg C for the out-of-plane bending mode. Therefore the damper operational temperature range is from 0 deg to 25 deg C.

11,13,14,16,17,18,22,27,29,30,31

Figure 17: Vibration Damper for New HST Solar Arrays

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Specific problems require specific, custom solutions. There is no one vibration suppression method that can usually meet all requirements for a certain problem. In general, passive systems perform best for higher frequencies, typically greater than 5 Hz, while active systems perform best for lower frequencies, typically lower than 5 Hz. As highlighted in this paper, most spacecraft solutions require a hybrid system (passive and active) to suppress the entire range of disturbance frequencies.

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